

PRINCIPAL MANAGEMENT IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF NEW STUDENT ADMISSION (PPDB) IN JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOLS

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Abstract

This study aims to understand and know the planning, organizing, implementing and supervising the management of school principals in implementing new student admissions (PPDB) at Ciparay 1 and Ciparay 3 junior high School, Bandung Regency. This research uses a qualitative approach through the case study method. The subjects in this study were school principals and the PPDB committee at Ciparay 1 and Ciparay 3 Junior high School, Bandung Regency. The data collection techniques used were observation, interviews, and documentation studies to obtain information about the management of school principals in implementing new student admissions (PPDB) at Ciparay 1 and Ciparay 3 Junior high School, Bandung Regency. The results of this study indicate that: (1) Planning is always carried out by the school principal by compiling the School Work Plan (RKS) as outlined in the Medium Term Work Plan (RKJM), The annual work plan (RKT) and School Activity Plan and Budget (RKAS), (2) Organizing is carried out by forming a PPDB committee, drafting a committee decree and creating a PPDB program, (3) Implementation starting with the registration stage and receiving files, the selection stage up to the announcement stage, (4) Supervision is carried out with evaluation, reflection and follow-up activities.

Keywords: Principal Management, New Student Admissions (PPDB).

A. INTRODUCTION

Obtaining education is a human right of every Indonesian citizen and for this reason every Indonesian citizen has the right to obtain quality education in accordance with their interests and talents regardless of social status, economic status, ethnicity, ethnicity, religion and gender. The government strives to provide education to all citizens through equal access to education. By having equal access to education, Indonesian citizens will have life skills, thus encouraging the establishment of holistic human development as well as a civil and modern society imbued with the values of Pancasila, as mandated in Law No. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System. The success of increasing access to education has a positive impact on the quality of human resources and economic growth. Increasing access and equal distribution of the quality of education is a mandate of the 1945 Constitution to provide opportunities for every community to fulfill their basic rights to obtain education in order to improve the quality of life for the welfare of humanity. Increasing access to education is shown by the increasing participation of the school-age population receiving education. Completing access to education is a

priority for educational development in Indonesia.

Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System which explains that the aim of National education is to develop the potential of students to become human beings who believe and are devoted to God Almighty, have noble character, are healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent. and become democratic and responsible citizens.

Students are an important component in education which is always a shared responsibility to provide the best for their future. For this reason, educational phenomena are descriptions of educational activities with all their problems and achievements in providing learning to students.

The annual acceptance of new students (PPDB) which is organized by the government and schools is not without problems, because competition between one school and another causes a struggle to get the best students. In fact, schools as formal educational institutions that are trusted by the community have responsibilities that must be carried out consistently by their managers. Schools are the spearhead for national education because indicators of educational success can only be measured after the school (at various levels) has carried out an evaluation process both locally and nationally.

Many children have ideal dreams of what they want to be when they grow up. One of the most important lessons about success is a simple principle called keep trying. In order for children to survive and succeed in this competitive world, they must learn to keep trying and not give up. One way that principals influence student success at school is by building, encouraging and maintaining focus on school goals and overall student achievement.

One of the vital things in student management is management which consists of planning new students, coaching and graduating in accordance with national education standards. An interesting phenomenon in student management is the planning of new students at the start of each new school year or what is known as PPDB. The acceptance of new students that has occurred so far has become an important agenda in the National Education work calendar and educational calendar, because this process is the first selection of prospective students who will enter school. The challenge of getting quality input through recruitment that takes place during New Student Admissions requires a careful and gradual planning system as well as serious attention from all school components so that the goals to be achieved are achieved.

To create an educational institution that can produce new human seeds like the ones above, it is necessary to hold a process for accepting quality new students. Because the factors that influence the success of an education are not only seen in terms of the education provided but also from the design of New Student Admissions held by the school. New Student Admission Design is what is meant by determining the criteria for prospective students who will be accepted. Such as economic, environmental, gender, achievement targets, etc. The recruitment stage is from the start of searching for students until the submission of the registration form or application. Meanwhile, the procurement

of new student admissions can be carried out by schools, collectives or recruitment agencies themselves.

Admission of New Students is an important part of the overall plan to increase and determine the maximum distribution of each who is capable of meeting institutional goals. The root problems behind this research are: first, based on 2020 Dapodikdasmen data, it is stated that the number of public and private junior high schools that have operational permits in Bandung district is 340 schools, divided into 78 state schools and 262 private schools. With the relatively small number of public schools, the Bandung district government took the initiative to build 16 proposed new schools spread across various areas of Bandung district with the aim of equalizing education for the community.

This policy has of course reaped pros and cons in the community, especially for private schools located in the area around the proposed new school building. As is known, there are 262 private schools spread across Bandung district, ranging from small private schools to private schools which in fact can be said to be favorite private schools that have good quality.

Second, there is a tendency for students' parents to prefer private schools that have high capabilities compared to state schools. This proves that the formation of children's character will be easier to develop in a school environment based on an Integrated Islamic school for the reason of instilling religious values that are stronger in an Islamic cultural environment. Specifically for Bandung district, especially in Ciparay district, it can be seen that there tend to be more students in private schools than students in state schools. The number of students in private schools is twice as large as students in public schools.

Third, many students do not continue their education from elementary to middle school. This is caused by many factors, including parents' economic factors which tend to be low, making it impossible to continue school. Apart from that, there are environmental factors where for rural environmental factors, they prefer to get married and help their parents/family financially by working part time. As can be seen from the diagram below, it is stated that there are 0.14% of students who have dropped out of junior high school or around 13,716 students in the Bandung district. Apart from that, there were 6.21% or around 208,157 people who did not continue to high school/vocational school equivalent after they graduated.

Based on Minister of Education and Culture Regulation No. 1 of 2021 concerning PPDB, it is stated that the PPDB route is divided into 4 types, namely zoning, affirmation, achievement and transfer of parental duties. In reality, students who are not absorbed in state schools go to private schools. Currently, many private schools offer better quality than state schools. Even several elite private schools with complete facilities offer superior programs even though they have to pay a nominal fee. So this is enough for parents of students to register their children at the school. For parents who do not have an adequate budget, it is considered sufficient to enroll their children in lower middle school private schools on the grounds that there are no fees and rely on education assistance cards from the government or government scholarships.

This phenomenon is quite interesting to discuss considering the lack of public trust in state schools. The school principal is required to maximize the various facilities owned by state schools to maximize the students who enter the school each year. The principal's ability to manage schools, especially state schools, really supports school quality. One aspect that must be considered is the ability to plan, organize, implement and evaluate PPDB activities every year.

Ideally, state schools can accommodate students according to the facilities the school has. With the existence of a zoning system, schools must better prepare facilities that support PPDB activities such as using appropriate applications, adequate operator staff, a solid committee team so that it will make it easier for parents of students in the process of accepting new students.

Because in reality, based on the evaluation of previous year's PPDB activities, parents encountered several obstacles in implementing PPDB such as servers that often had problems, parents who did not understand IT, miscommunication between parents and the PPDB committee, and many more.

These obstacles should have been detected by the school principal, so that the managerial abilities of the school principal in this case are really needed so that the school's goal of obtaining maximum students can be achieved.

The central role of the school principal will be to determine whether or not the number of students the school has will increase, because this will automatically impact the receipt of BOS funds which will be distributed to the school. This relates to the function of the school principal as an Educator, Manager, Administrator, Supervisor, Leader, Innovator and Motivator.

Ciparay 1 State Junior High School is the best public school in Bandung district, Ciparay sub-district, considering its strategic location on Jalan Laswi which is the road connecting Ciparay and Majalaya sub-districts. So that it can be reached by all levels of local society. Currently there are 24 classes with around 30-35 students in each class.

On the other hand, Ciparay 3 State Junior High School is a public school located on top of the mountains in the Rancakole area with a land area of around 1 hectare. It is claimed to be the largest school in Bandung district. Currently it only has 18 classes with a total of around 30-35 students. This condition is said to have decreased compared to the number of students in the previous year.

The background to this problem, researchers assess that the managerial abilities of school principals greatly influence the implementation of student admissions each year. Considering the important role of the school principal, researchers are interested in conducting research entitled "School Principal Management in the Implementation of New Student Admissions at Ciparay 1 State Junior High School and Ciparay 3 State Junior High School.

B. THEORETICAL BASIS

1. Education Management

Education management is a process or management system. Education management as a process or system of organization and improvement of humanity in relation to an education system. Management activities in an education system aim to implement a good teaching and learning process, which includes: a) Curriculum programs which include curriculum administration, delivery methods, evaluation systems, guidance systems; b) Employment program; c) Procurement and maintenance program for educational facilities and equipment; d) Financing program; e) Community relations program.

The systems approach in education management is a result of the approach adopted in the education system. The education system is a unity of various elements which are interconnected and dependent on each other in carrying out their duties to achieve the goals of the system. Elements from outside that enter the system and then undergo a process are called outputs (Oemar Hamalik, 2007:78).

- a. Objectives of Educational Management: In general, the objectives of educational management in the learning process are to develop a management system which includes: 1) Administration and organization of the curriculum; 2) Management and personnel; 3) Management of facilities and infrastructure; 4) Financing management; 5) Management of educational media; 6) Management of relationships with the community, which is management of the implementation of relevant, effective and efficient learning processes that support the achievement of educational goals. Then, if we look more specifically, the aim of implementing educational management is to create a management system that is relevant, effective and efficient which can be implemented by achieving targets with an organizational structure pattern of clear division of tasks and responsibilities between program leaders, trainers, facilitators, library staff and staff. other technical, administrative staff and supervisory staff. Apart from that, educational management aims to facilitate the management of educational programs and the implementation of learning processes based on an active student learning approach (Oemar Hamalik, 2007:80).
- b. Educational Management Function: Educational management has an integrated function with the educational process, especially with the management of the learning process. In this connection, there are several educational management functions, namely: 1) Planning function, including various activities to determine needs, determine strategies for achieving goals, determine the content of educational programs and so on. In the context of management, it is necessary to carry out planning activities, which reach into the future to improve the situation and meet future needs, determine the goals to be pursued, develop a program which includes the approach, type and sequence of activities, determine the required cost plan, and determine the schedule and process. Work; 2) Organizational functions, including management of personnel, facilities and infrastructure, distribution of tasks and responsibilities, in integral management. For this reason, activities need to be carried

out, such as: identifying types and tasks of responsibility and authority, formulating work relationship rules; 3) Coordination function, which seeks to stabilize various tasks, responsibilities and authorities to ensure the implementation and success of educational programs; 4) Motivational Function, which is intended to increase process efficiency and the success of training programs. This is necessary in connection with the division of tasks and responsibilities and authority, so that there is an increase in personal activities, which in turn is expected to increase the success of the program; 5) Control function, which seeks to supervise, assess, monitor and correct weaknesses in the education management system (Oemar Hamalik, 2007:81).

2. Headmaster

In the Big Indonesian Dictionary as quoted by Wahjosumidja in Ahmad Susanto (2016:34) Principal comes from two words, namely "Head" and "School". The word Head can be interpreted as the chairman or leader in an organization or institution. Meanwhile, a school is an institution where it is a place to receive and give lessons. According to Wahjosumidja in Ahmad Susanto (2016:13), the principal is a functional teacher who is given the task of leading a school, which carries out the teaching and learning process, or interaction between teachers and students. Rahman stated that the Principal is a teacher (functional position) who is appointed to occupy a structural position (Principal) in the school. (Nur Aedi, 2016:35) The definition of a school principal is in accordance with the Minister of National Education Regulation No. 28 of 2010 concerning the Assignment of Teachers as School/Madrasah Principals, Article 1 paragraph 1, namely: School/Madrasah Principals are teachers who are given additional duties to lead kindergarten/raudhotul athfal (TK/RA), special kindergarten (TKLB), ibtdaiyah school/madrasah (SD/MI), special elementary school (SDLB), junior high school/tsanawiyah madrasah (SMP/ MTs), special junior high school (SMPLB), high school/madrasah Aliyah (SMA/MA), vocational high school/vocational madrasah aliyah (SMK/MAK), special high school (SMALB) which is not an international standard school (SBI) or which are not developed into international standard schools (SBI). Article 12 paragraph 1 of Government Regulation Number 28 of 1990 concerning Basic Education states that school principals are responsible for organizing educational activities, school administration, developing other educational staff and utilizing and maintaining facilities and infrastructure.

The principal is the determining factor in managing education in his school in order to achieve educational goals. Therefore, school principals are required to have various abilities in leading educational management, adequate knowledge and skills. The principal is one of the components of education that plays a very important role in improving the quality of education. This is as explained by the Adjunct Lecturer Team in Ahmad Susanto (2016: 13) that educational leadership is the ability to drive the implementation of education, so that the educational goals that have been set can be achieved effectively and efficiently. Thus, it is clear that the Principal is someone who is given the authority to lead a public or private institution, of course who has adequate knowledge, abilities and skills and has a lot of experience in the scope of education.

The main duties of the Principal are more focused on learning and administrative functions. Tasks in the field of learning are the main duties of the Principal. The Principal's attention is more focused on thinking about the smooth running of learning and administrative functions. (Ahmad Susanto, 2016:24) Specifically, the Principal is tasked with: a) Determining school goals; b) Developing and encouraging students' hopes to achieve success; c) Determining and encouraging high academic standards; d) Maintaining the weight of teaching hours; e) Requires the existence of curricular knowledge and its thorough delivery; f) Conditioning the curriculum; g) Stimulate and assist teaching improvement; h) Carry out supervision and evaluation of teaching; i) Creating a productive work environment and climate. According to Mc Crudy in Ahmad Susanto (2016:13) apart from the learning tasks mentioned above, the principal has administrative duties, namely the principal must focus himself in six areas, namely: people, media learning, resources, quality of supervision, coordination of school activities, and problem solving. According to the Ministry of National Education (2006:32), the principal has several main roles, namely:

- a. Educators According to Wahjosumdjo in an article entitled School Principals as Educators quoted by Nur Aedi (2016:45), that: Understanding the meaning of educator is not enough to adhere to the conditions contained in the definition of educator, but rather to study its relationship to the meaning of education, educational facilities, and how the educational strategy is implemented. For this purpose, the school principal must try to instill, promote and improve at least four kinds of values, namely coaching, mental, moral, physical and artistic. Learning activities are the core of the educational process and teachers are the main implementers and developers of the curriculum in schools. School principals who demonstrate high commitment and focus on curriculum development and learning activities in their schools will of course pay close attention to the level of competence of their teachers, and will also always try to facilitate and encourage teachers to continuously improve their competence, so that learning activities can run effectively. and efficient. According to Nur Aedi (2016:45) School principals as educators or educators, must carry out planning, implementation and evaluation of learning activities. As is done by teachers. Apart from that, as an educator, the Principal's function is to provide guidance to teachers, students and other school staff. In order to increase teacher competency and ability, the Principal can make the following efforts: 1) To broaden their knowledge, teachers are involved in training activities and provide opportunities for teachers to develop their knowledge to a higher level of education; 2) Be transparent regarding the results of student learning evaluations displayed on the notice board, with the aim of increasing student learning motivation; 3) Using and utilizing learning time effectively, namely by encouraging teachers to start and end learning activities on time.
- b. Manager In managing educational staff, one of the tasks that the Principal must carry out is to carry out maintenance and professional development activities for teachers. In this case, the Principal should be able to facilitate and provide ample opportunities for teachers to be able to carry out professional development activities through various educational and training activities, both carried out at school, such as school-level

Subject Teacher Conferences (MGMP), in-house training, professional discussions and so on, or through education and training activities outside of school, such as continuing education or participating in various training activities organized by other parties. The principal as a manager has a role in determining the school management process. The success or failure of school objectives can be influenced by the Principal's ability to carry out management functions, which consist of planning, organizing, implementing and supervising. (Nur Aedi, 2016:46) In accordance with the Decree of the Minister of National Education regarding managerial competence, one of which is that the Principal must be able to carry out school management, and his performance must be visible in carrying out the areas of managerial work. Stoner also argues in Nur Aedi (2016:46) that: There are eight types of manager functions in an organization, namely the Principal: working with and through other people, being responsible and accountable, able to deal with various limited conditions, thinking analytically and conceptual, as a mediator, as a politician, as a diplomat, and functions as a decision maker.

- c. The Principal Administrator plays the role of financial manager of cost factors. How much a school can allocate a budget to increase teacher competency will of course influence the level of competency of its teachers. Therefore, the Principal should be able to allocate an adequate budget in an effort to increase teacher competency. (Ahmad Susanto, 2016:16) The principal as an administrator has activities related to school administration activities, including recording and documenting various schools. The principal must have the ability to manage the curriculum, finances, students and archive administration. This will support the quality of schools, if done effectively and efficiently. The principal must be able to coordinate the administration of the school and create an orderly, smooth and timely administration. In broad terms, the Principal is the person who has the highest policy in the school, the Principal also carries out environmental analysis (social, cultural, political and economic) and develops strategies for implementing educational programs to achieve educational goals, while in the narrow sense, the Principal has responsibility regarding school administration work and learning activities.
- d. Supervisor Supervision is very important for the Principal to determine the extent to which teachers are able to carry out learning. Supervision carried out by the Principal can be carried out through class visits to observe and use the methods, media used and student involvement in the learning process. From the results of this supervision, we can identify the teacher's weaknesses and strengths in carrying out learning, the level of teacher competency mastery, then solutions, coaching and follow-up efforts can be made so that teachers can correct deficiencies in implementing learning. According to Nur Aedi (2016:48), the important role of the Principal as a supervisor is to provide contributions that are nurturing, guiding and directing the development of school personnel. Contributions given to educators and other education personnel function to develop the learning process in a better direction and help improve the quality of education. Permendiknas No. 13 of 2007 concerning School/Madrasah Principal Standards, that the duties of the Principal as a supervisor are: 1) Planning an

- academic supervision program in order to increase teacher professionalism 2) Carrying out academic supervision of teachers using appropriate supervision approaches and techniques 3) Following up the results of academic supervision of teachers in order to increase teacher professionalism.
- e. Leader In order to improve teacher competency, a school principal can apply his leadership flexibly and appropriately, adapted to existing conditions and needs. As a leader, the Principal's role is to mobilize the school's potential and influence educators and education staff to work according to their duties to achieve educational goals. Thus the Principal must have extensive knowledge and leadership, so that he is able to influence, mobilize and control human resources with his duties and responsibilities effectively and efficiently.
 - f. Innovator The principal as an innovator has the task of being able to renew learning activities and other educational activities. Apart from that, the Principal must also have ideas and strategic plans to support the implementation of school programs, be able to create harmonious relationships with fellow school members, and be able to develop creative and innovative learning models and methods.
 - g. Motivator The principal as a motivator plays a role in providing encouragement and enthusiasm to educators and education staff in carrying out their respective duties and functions. The motivation provided can be in the form of creating communication relationships and a school climate that is harmonious, intensive, respectful or assisting in providing learning media. Therefore, school principals must have the right strategy to provide intensive and extensive motivation which is one of the most dominant factors in moving other people to work well in accordance with their duties and responsibilities.
 - h. Formal Officials The principal can be said to be a formal official because the appointment process is carried out through established procedures. As a formal official, the Principal has certain duties and must be responsible to his superiors and subordinates within the school environment. According to Wahjosumidjo, quoted by Nur Aedi (2016: 50), like other formal leaders, school principals will be successful in carrying out their duties if they always pay attention to seven very influential things, namely: 1) Legislation, policies and applicable regulation; 2) Variables that occur inside and outside school; 3) Interaction between human resources, systems and various types of equipment; 4) Effectiveness; 5) Problems of profit and loss; 6) Trusted and experienced; 7) Authority, status, stress and conflict.
 - i. Creating a work climate. A conducive work culture and climate will enable each teacher to be more motivated to demonstrate superior performance, accompanied by efforts to improve their competence. Therefore, in an effort to create a conducive work culture and climate, school principals should pay attention to the following principles: 1) Teachers will work harder if the activities carried out are interesting and enjoyable; 2) The objectives of the activity need to be clearly formulated and informed to teachers so that they know the purpose of the work, teachers can be involved in preparing these objectives; 3) Giving rewards is better than punishment, but punishment is also

necessary; 4) Try to meet the teacher's socio-psycho-physical needs so that a decision can be made.

- j. Entrepreneurial In applying the principles of entrepreneurship linked to increasing teacher competence, school principals must be able to create innovation, comparative advantage, and take advantage of various opportunities. School principals with a strong entrepreneurial attitude will have the courage to make innovative changes in their schools, including changes in matters related to the learning process and teacher competency. The functions of the Principal's educational leadership are as follows: 1) Creating an atmosphere of brotherhood, cooperation with a full sense of freedom; 2) Helping the group to organize itself, namely participating in providing group stimulation in setting and explaining goals; 3) Assist the group in establishing work procedures, namely assisting the group in analyzing the situation to then determine which procedures are the most practical and effective; 4) Responsible for making decisions together with the group; 5) Provide opportunities for groups to learn from experience. The leader has the responsibility to train the group to be aware of the process and content being carried out and have the courage to assess the results honestly and objectively; 6) Responsible for developing and maintaining the existence of the organization.

C. RESEARCH METHODS

This research method uses a qualitative research approach with descriptive research methods. The data collection techniques used in this research were observation, interviews and documentation studies.

The first steps of this research from pre-field are preparing a plan, selecting a location, arranging permits, assessing the situation, selecting informants and preparing instruments. Then the second is field, namely understanding and entering the field and data collection, then the third is data processing, namely data reduction, data display and data analysis, drawing conclusions and narrating the results.

The data collection instruments used in this research were recording devices and writing instruments as supporting tools to obtain the required information.

D. RESEARCH RESULTS

Based on the results of observations, interviews and documentation studies carried out, the following research findings were obtained:

1. Planning

Planning in school principal management during PPDB implementation begins with preparing a School Activity Plan (RKS) which is contained in the Medium Term Work Plan (RKJM), Annual Work Plan (RKT) and School Activity and Budget Plan (RKAS). In this school principal's work program, new student admission activities are determined starting from activity planning to budget/cost planning. So everything is well planned. With this planning, the school principal and the New Student Admissions committee have used

existing resources to achieve the goal of New Student Admissions. Planning for the Admission of New Students is the beginning of the entire series of school principal management because with the planning for the Admission of New Students, the activities of the school principal and the New Student Admissions committee are in the form of acceptance, selection and placement, as well as other activities related to the Admission of Students. Just more focused. A plan as a follow-up to the annual program whose form of implementation has been agreed, while the time is adjusted to the National Education Calendar.

2. Organizing

Every new school year, the school is busy with accepting new students. Before this activity begins, the school principal first forms a committee. The organization of the school principal's management in the implementation of New Student Admission is carried out by forming a new student admission committee meeting which is led directly by the school principal. Before announcing the acceptance of new students, the school first held a meeting to form a New Student Admissions committee and at the same time discussed the issue of accepting new students which was attended by all teachers and school leaders. In the meeting the school formed a New Student Admissions committee which was directly coordinated by a representative. The principal is assisted by appointed teachers at this meeting and at the same time also discusses the number of students to be accepted by adjusting existing local capacity. From observations it was found that before accepting new students, management and teachers first held a meeting to discuss various issues that were considered important in relation to the process and determination of criteria for accepting prospective new students. After the committee is formed, the committee then makes preparations. The smooth and successful work of a work team depends on the proportionality and professionalism of the division of work. This division of work is intended so that the executive committees do not overlap in carrying out their tasks, so each task is determined through the division of sections.

3. Actuating

The implementation of Admission of New Students in Middle School is carried out in two types, namely online and offline. Online acceptance of new students can be done by prospective registrants verifying data by filling in the National Student Identification Number (NISN) and Population Identification Number (NIK), if the data appears then they can continue with creating an account for registration for New Student Admissions, if the data appears Not registered at the time of verification. Prospective registrants can go to the destination school to get an account.

Meanwhile, the implementation of offline acceptance of new students can be done by coming directly to the school bringing the required physical documents according to the route chosen. Then verify student data by inputting the National Student Identification Number (NISN) and Population Identification Number (NIK) in the PPDB application by the school operator. After that, determine the coordinates of the student's house on the map according to the address on the family card document. print the zoning confirmation form document and statement of absolute responsibility.

4. Supervision

PPDB supervision/control is carried out through daily monitoring and evaluation. Supervision is carried out by internal and external parties. The school's internal parties are supervised by the principal and assisted by the control section. Meanwhile, external supervision takes the form of monitoring from the Bandung District Education Office, even the mass media and the public using PPDB services. Every evaluation result carried out by the school is followed up and a report is made to the Bandung District Education Office.

E. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research into the management of school principals in the implementation of PPDB at Ciparay 1 State Junior High School and Ciparay 3 State Junior High School, it can be concluded that both of them carry out management processes starting from planning, organizing, implementing and monitoring/evaluating. In the planning process, the school principal prepares a Medium Term Work Plan (RKJM), Annual Work Plan (RKT) and School Activity and Budget Plan (RKAS). During the organizing process, the school principal held a meeting with the teacher council to form a PPDB committee. Apart from the formation of the PPDB committee, this meeting also discussed the capacity of students that the school could accommodate according to the facilities the school had. Then in this meeting, possible obstacles faced during the implementation of the PPDB were also discussed and solutions were sought that might be implemented in the field. The next process is implementation. In this process, PPDB can be carried out in two ways, namely through offline and online activities. And the last is the monitoring/evaluation stage. In this process, PPDB activities are monitored and evaluated by internal and external parties. The internal parties are the principal and the controlling section. Meanwhile, external parties are the Bandung district education office, even the mass media and the public who use PPDB services. The results of this monitoring/evaluation are used as follow-up material for the implementation of PPDB in the following year.

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